

EFFECT OF BACILLUS MEGATERIUM AND BACILLUS STEAROTHERMOPHILUS ON THE CHLORIDE PENETRATION RESISTANCE OF CALCINED CLAY CEMENT MORTAR

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14020356

ABSTRACT

The durability of concrete structures, particularly their resistance to chloride penetration, is crucial for ensuring long-term performance, especially in marine and other chloride-rich environments. Calcined clay, recognized for its pozzolanic properties, is increasingly utilized as a sustainable supplementary cementitious material (SCM) due to its availability and beneficial effects on mechanical properties and durability. However, the potential for further enhancement with the incorporation of bacteria remains underexplored. This research investigated the impact of microbial-induced calcite precipitation (MICP) facilitated by *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* on the chloride penetration resistance of calcined clay cement mortars. Mortar specimens were infused with varying concentrations (10^{-5} , 10^{-7} , 10^{-9}) of *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* were prepared under different pH conditions (pH 4 and pH 9). These specimens were coated with epoxy in all but one face to allow for unidirectional ingress of chloride and then cured for periods of 7, 28, and 90 days. Chloride penetration tests were conducted to assess the depth of chloride ingress, and the results were compared with those of control specimens. The findings reveal that the inclusion of *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* significantly reduces chloride penetration in calcined clay cement mortar. The effectiveness of these bacteria varied with concentration and pH levels, with higher bacterial concentrations generally resulting in better performance. *Bacillus Megaterium* showed superior efficacy at lower pH levels, while *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* exhibited enhanced performance at higher pH levels. In conclusion, the incorporation of *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* into calcined clay cement mortar presents a promising approach to improving chloride penetration resistance. This microbial intervention has the potential to extend the service life of concrete structures, offering a sustainable and effective solution for enhancing durability in chloride-rich environments.

Keywords: *Bacillus Megaterium*, *Bacillus Stearothermophilus*, Chloride penetration, Calcined clay mortar

INTRODUCTION

Concrete durability is a critical concern in the construction industry, especially in environments exposed to aggressive agents such as chloride ions, which can significantly reduce the lifespan of concrete structures by inducing corrosion of the reinforcing steel. The ingress of chloride ions into concrete is one of the primary causes of reinforcement corrosion, leading to cracking, spalling, and eventual structural failure. Chloride ions can penetrate into concrete through various pathways, including cracks, joints, and the surface, and can cause corrosion of the reinforcing steel (Kuang, *et al.*, 2022). Thus, enhancing the chloride penetration resistance of concrete is vital for ensuring the longevity and safety of infrastructure.

Calcined clay has gained attention as a sustainable supplementary cementitious material (SCM) due to its pozzolanic properties (Beuntner *et al.*, 2019; Schulze and Rickert, 2018; Akindahunsi *et al.*, 2020; Jaskulski, *et al.*, 2020), which improve the mechanical properties and durability of concrete (Meddah, *et al.*, 2023; Boakye and Khorami, 2023; Kafodya *et al.*, 2023). The use of calcined clay not only helps in reducing the carbon footprint associated with cement production but also enhances the performance characteristics of the mortar (Dawood *et al.*, 2022; Alghamdi *et al.*, 2023). Replacing a portion of cement with calcined clay in mortar mixes can lead to a significant reduction in CO₂ emission (Dawood *et al.*, 2022; Alghamdi *et al.*, 2023). The pozzolanic reaction between calcined clay and calcium hydroxide produces additional calcium silicate hydrates, enhancing the microstructure and mechanical

performance (Alghamdi *et al.*, 2023; Dousti, *et al.*, 2022). However, the potential for further enhancement through innovative techniques such as microbial-induced calcite precipitation (MICP) remains an area for exploration.

MICP is a process by which certain bacteria precipitate calcium carbonate (calcite) within the concrete matrix, filling pores and cracks, and thereby enhancing the material's durability (Akindahunsi *et al.*, 2021; Rahul-Rollakanti and Srinivasu, 2021; Zehner, *et al.*, 2020). This process involves the interaction between the bacteria and calcium ions present in the concrete, resulting in the formation of calcium carbonate crystals. The bacteria, which are typically urease-producing, hydrolyze urea into ammonia and carbonate ions, which then react with calcium ions to form calcium carbonate (Muhammad, *et al.*, 2021; Jose *et al.*, 2019; Zhang *et al.*, 2023). *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* are known for their calcite-precipitating capabilities and have shown promise in improving the properties of concrete. The application of these bacteria in calcined clay cement mortar could offer a novel approach to enhancing chloride penetration resistance.

This study investigated the effect of *Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* on the chloride penetration resistance of calcined clay cement mortar. By incorporating these bacteria at different concentrations and pH levels, and curing the specimens over varying periods, the study aims to understand the extent to which these microbial interventions can improve durability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used in the study of the effect of calcite precipitating Bacteria (*Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus*) on the mechanical properties of calcined-clay cement included cement (Portland cement of grade 42.5N), fine aggregates (obtained from local construction sites around and bacteria (*Bacillus Megaterium* and *Bacillus Stearothermophilus*). *Bacillus Megaterium* is strictly an aerobic gram-positive rod-shaped bacterium found in the soil. *Megaterium* is a spore forming bacterium that can stay dormant for several years with the ability to withstand high temperatures and alkalinity. However, the thermophilic, aerobic bacterium, *bacillus stearothermophilus* forms ellipsoidal spores that spread the sporangium. *Bacillus Stearothermophilus* are found in soil, it is a diverse species that is distinguished by its lowest growth temperature of 40°C, optimum development temperature of 65–75°C, and limited tolerance to acid.

Calcination of Clay

The clay sample was grounded into fine powder and sundried to remove any moisture. Subsequently, the dried sample underwent calcination at a temperature of 800°C. This calcination process was conducted at the Nigeria Building and Road Research Institute in Ota, utilizing an electrically powered furnace capable of reaching temperatures up to 1500°C. During calcination, the

temperature was gradually increased at a rate of 130°C per minute from ambient temperature to 800°C, where it was maintained for two hours. After this period, the sample was allowed to cool within the furnace until it reached ambient temperature, after which it was further allowed to cool to room temperature and then packed into a plastic container.

Bacteria Culture and Growth

For the purpose of growing bacteria, two culture media were put up. NH₄-YE nutrient broth medium and NH₄-YE agar plate media (solid medium). The medium was made up of calcium lactate, yeast extract, nitrogen, ammonium sulphate (NH₄SO₄), and tris buffer solution. Each of these ingredients was weighed out and dissolved in an equal volume of distilled water. The nutritional broth was autoclaved at 121°C for 15 minutes before being allowed to cool to room temperature. The prepared nutrient broth medium, *bacillus megaterium* and *bacillus stearothermophilus* were subsequently subcultured.

Using a sterile needle or loop, the media was injected from the petri plate and serially diluted to yield 10⁻⁵, 10⁻⁷, and 10⁻⁹ cells/ml. A subsequent inoculation (1:10) was then made into a 250 ml conical flask that had 200 ml of culture material. To prevent contamination, cotton wool was then used to cover the conical flask. The conical flasks were placed on an orbital shaker set at 130–300 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 28 days after being incubated at 30°C to guarantee the highest possible rate of bacterial growth.

Preliminary Analysis on Aggregate and Cement

The preliminary tests carried out on the fine aggregate and cement used for the preparation of the mortar specimens were specific gravity, fineness modulus, and sieve analysis. The specific gravity was analysed to determine the density of fine aggregates in relation to the density of water. It provided insights into the particle packing and overall density of the fine aggregates. This is essential for proportioning concrete or mortar mixtures, influencing both the fresh and hardened properties. The fineness modulus was determined to determine the measure of the fineness or coarseness of the fine aggregate. It helps assess the particle size distribution of the aggregates. A measure of the time it takes for the cement paste to set after mixing with water (initial setting time) was carried out. Furthermore, a measure of the time taken in which the cement paste completely loses its plasticity and becomes rigid (final setting time) was carried out. Standard consistency was carried out to determine the percentage of water required for normal cement paste consistency. Similar to the specific gravity of fine aggregates, specific gravity of cement was determined to investigate the density of cement used in relation to water.

A variety of biochemical assays were performed to evaluate the bacteria's capacity to precipitate calcite (CaCO₃), including microscopy, the Gram's stain test, the Sulphur Indole Motility test, and the Triple Sugar Iron test. Table 1 shows the biochemical confirmation and Sulphur indole

motility test results, Table 2 shows triple sugar iron test results and Table 3 shows the production of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) precipitate.

Preparation of Mortar Specimens

Component of mortar (cement, sand water/bacterial solution) was batched by weight. The mix ratio of 1:3 of cement and sand and water-cement ratio of 0.5 was adopted for the cylindrical shaped specimens. A total of twelve (12) specimens of the cylindrical mortar were ponded in sodium

guaranteeing that every specimen had the same measurements.

A chloride solution was then applied to the prepared test specimens. Twenty litres of water were mixed with 750 g of chloride to create the solution. To make sure the specimens were completely submerged, they were immersed in the sodium chloride solution. The test was carried out in a controlled environment to ensure uniformity throughout the examination. The test specimens were submerged for 90

Table 1: Biochemical Confirmation and Sulphur Indole Motility Test Results

Isolate codes	Gram's reaction	Cellular Morphology	Motility	Indole	Sulphide	Calcium production	Identity
Bacillus Stearothermophilus (ATCC)	+	Cocci	+	+	+	+	Bacillus confirmed
Bacillus Megaterium (ATCC)	+	Cocci	+	+	+	+	Bacillus Confirmed

Table 2: Shows Triple Sugar Iron Test Results

Isolate Codes	H ₂ S Production	Gas Production
Bacillus Stearothermophilus	+	-
Bacillus Megaterium	+	+

Table 3: Production of Calcium Carbonate (CaCO₃) Precipitate

Days	Day 0	Day 3	Day 5	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21	Day 28
Results	-	-	-	-	+	++	++

chloride solution

Curing and Coating of Mortar Specimens for Chloride Penetration Test

Before ponding the specimens in a salt solution, they underwent a 28-day initial stage of curing in water before ponded in sodium chloride solution for 90 days.

The sodium chloride solution was prepared by adding 750 g of salt to 20 litres of potable water. Following the initial curing step, the cylindrical mortar specimens' surfaces received two coats of epoxy sealer, leaving only one circular surface uncovered. After the initial coating layer had fully dried, a second coating was applied.

The purpose of the uncoated surface is to allow sodium chloride ions, to seep into the mortar specimens from the salt solution in which they had been ponded.

Sodium Chloride Penetration Test

Among a number of techniques, the salt ponding or normal test (AASHTO T259) is a widely used method for assessing chloride penetrability. Test specimens were prepared in compliance with the experiment's criteria and requirements before the chloride penetration test got underway. These cylindrical specimens were taken from the materials that were being studied. They were meticulously carved and moulded to the appropriate shapes and sizes,

days in the sodium chloride solution to simulate prolonged exposure to settings containing chloride as depicted in Figure 1. The experiment's goals and the anticipated environmental circumstances that the materials could face in practical uses were taken into consideration while determining the exposure time. Following the exposure time, the two test specimens were taken out of their respective solutions and their characteristics were carefully investigated. Visual observations and measurements of the sodium chloride content were among the data gathered during the test that were assembled for analysis.

In order to determine the materials' resistance to sodium chloride penetration, the mortar specimens were sliced into 8 slices of 20 mm. The assessment of salt penetration at different depths is possible with deeper slices. This is critical to comprehending the mortar's resistance to chloride ion infiltration over its thickness, particularly in high-chloride-ion exposure situations like coastal locations. The test specimens' resistance to chloride penetration were evaluated and the findings were helpful in understanding how the materials performed in situations exposed to salt.

Procedure for Chloride Penetration Test of Mortar Specimen

Using non-iodized salt, a ponding solution with a 3% sodium chloride content was made. For 90 days, the covered mortar specimens were submerged in saline water. A few

weeks before the 90 days ponding period came to an end, the salt water was replaced with freshly produced salt water. After ponding for 90 days, the specimens were taken out of the salt water, dried, and sliced into 10 mm slices, with the exception of the initial layer, which was 15 mm thick (Figure 1). From each specimen, eight to ten layers were cut down to a depth of 14 cm. After being appropriately labelled, the layers were crushed (10 g taken from each sample) was then combined with 100 millilitres of distilled water, properly stirred, and allowed to settle. Following a 15-minute soak in distilled water, the mixture's solution was titrated using Mohr's technique for sodium ions and the titre values were observed and recorded.

At various concentrations and pH values, the chloride concentration profiles were determined. The *Bacillus megaterium*-infused specimens had pH values of 4 and 9, and their concentrations were 10^{-9} , 10^{-7} , and 10^{-5} . *Bacillus stearothermophilus* was added into the specimens at doses of 10^{-9} , 10^{-7} , and 10^{-5} at pH 4 and pH 9, respectively. A common technique for determining how long mortar or concrete will last against ion intrusion from chloride is the chloride penetration test. It is well known that chloride ions, which are often present in saltwater and deicing solutions, are harmful for the longevity of mortar and concrete constructions. An environment with a lower pH (pH 4) is usually seen to be more acidic, whereas one with a higher pH (pH 9) is thought to be more alkaline. The effect of acid exposure may be evaluated with the use of the pH 4 test; this is especially important in certain industrial or environmental scenarios.

The examination of chloride penetration at various levels inside the mortar is made possible by slicing specimens at different depths, as seen in Figure 1. Slices that are deeper reveal more about how resistant the mortar is to chloride ions at lower depths.

Procedures to Determine Chlorides in Water using Mohr's Method

- i. 5 g of mortar cube was pounded using mortar and pestle which was then soaked in distilled water for 15 minutes.
- ii. 100 ml of bacterial mortar solution was collected and placed in a conical flask as shown in Figure 2.
- iii. 1ml of potassium chromate indicator was added
- iv. The above-mentioned was titrated to determine the titrated value.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the preliminary analysis of the sand and cement samples are shown in Table 4 and Table 5. The specific gravity of fine aggregate was found to be 2.64, which was between the range of 2.6 to 2.8, indicating that the fine aggregate was suitable for construction.

The Fineness modulus of the fine aggregates was found to be 2.72 as shown in table 4, indicating a fine to medium-fine gradation of the fine aggregate, which is critical for designing concrete mixes with optimal particle packing and workability. The Initial setting time of the cement was found to be 165 mins indicating a slow-setting cement, which can be advantageous in scenarios where extended workability is required. The final setting time of 360 minutes suggested a cement with a delayed setting characteristic, providing a more extended timeframe for placing and finishing concrete.

Standard consistency of paste was found to be 34% as shown on Table 5, indicating the water-cement ratio at which the cement paste exhibits normal consistency, which is vital for achieving desired workability in concrete. The specific gravity of the cement was found to be 3.15 indicating that the cement is denser than water.

Table 4: Properties of Fine Aggregates

Test / Condition	Properties
Specific Gravity of Fine Aggregates	2.64
Fineness Modulus	2.72

Table 5: Properties of Cement

Characteristics	Values
Initial Setting Time (mins)	165
Final Setting Time (mins)	360
Standard Consistency (%)	34
Specific Gravity	3.15

Particle Size Distribution of Fine Aggregates

The grain size distribution is shown in Table 6 and the grain size distribution curves are depicted in Figure 2. The results of sieve analysis as presented reveals the values of D_{60} , D_{30} , and D_{10} , as 0.48, 0.2 and 0.8 respectively in fine aggregates. These represent the particle sizes at which 10%, 30%, and 60% of the material is finer. In this study, D_{10} is 0.8, D_{30} is 0.2, and D_{60} is 0.48. According to Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), if Co-efficient of Uniformity (Cu) value of soil is range from 4 to 10 and co-efficient of curvature (Cc) value is range between 1 and 3 then, the soil particle is well-graded. But when Cu value is less than 4 and Cc value is less than 1, the soil particle is uniformly graded. The values of Cu and Cc according to calculations from Table 6 reveals that Cu and Cc of the fine aggregates to be 6.0 and 1.04 respectively indicating that the fine aggregate are well graded and therefore suitable for construction.

Chloride Ions Penetration Test

The chloride penetration profiles for the different samples are shown on Figures 4 and 5 for pH 4 and pH 9. They show the effect of the exposure medium and the w/c ratio on the chloride penetration profiles.

Table 6: Particle Size Parameter

Particle Size Parameter	Value
D ₁₀ (10% Passing)	0.8
D ₃₀ (30% Passing)	0.2
D ₆₀ (60% Passing)	0.48
Coefficient of Uniformity (Cu)	6.0
Coefficient of Curvature (Cc)	1.04

The results of the chloride penetration test provide insights into the resistance of the calcined clay cement mortar to chloride ion penetration. A lower depth of chloride penetration indicates better durability and resistance to chloride-induced deterioration. The varying concentrations of bacillus megaterium and bacillus stearothermophilus indicate their potential role in either enhancing or reducing the chloride resistance of the calcined clay cement mortars. A decrease in chloride penetration with the presence of these bacteria suggests a positive impact on durability at pH 4 and pH 9 as displayed in Figure 4 and Figure 5. By testing different concentrations of the bacteria, it can be assessed whether there is a concentration-dependent effect. Higher concentrations may offer more significant improvements in chloride resistance. The results of the chloride penetration test for various samples, including the control sample and those with different concentrations of bacillus megaterium and bacillus stearothermophilus at different pH levels, provide insights into the chloride resistance of the calcined clay cement mortar at different depths

Figure 2: Particle Size Distribution of Fine Aggregate

In the control sample, at the surface (15 mm depth), the concentration of chloride ions was relatively high at 404.87 mg/l. As the slices got deeper into the material, the concentration gradually decreased with increasing depth. At a depth of 150 mm, the concentration is significantly lower at 119.94 mg/l. For bacillus megaterium mortars at

pH 4, the chloride penetration and concentration are significantly reduced compared to the control sample. At the surface (15 mm depth), the concentration of chloride ions is reduced to 279.91 mg/l, lower than the control sample. As the slices got deeper into the material, the concentration decreased further. At 150 mm, the concentration is 79.98 mg/l. At pH 4, the specimens with different bacterial concentrations (10-5, 10-7, 10-9) generally exhibited a reduction in chloride concentrations compared to the control across all depths. The reduction is more pronounced at higher bacterial concentrations, indicating a positive correlation between bacterial dosage and chloride resistance. The highest concentration (10-5) consistently demonstrated the most significant reduction in chloride penetration.

The presence of bacillus stearothermophilus at pH 4 also results in a notable reduction in chloride concentration. At the surface (15 mm depth), the concentration was 264.92 mg/l, which is significantly lower than the control sample. Deeper within the material, the concentration continued to decrease, reaching 14.99 mg/l at 150 mm depth. Similar to bacillus megaterium, bacillus stearothermophilus at pH 4 results in a reduction in chloride penetration. However, unlike bacillus megaterium, higher bacterial concentrations generally correspond to more effective chloride resistance. The 10-5 concentration consistently exhibits the most significant reduction. When bacillus megaterium was introduced at pH 9, the reduction in chloride concentration was even more significant. At the surface (15 mm depth), the concentration was only 179.94 mg/l, considerably lower than the control sample. And as the slices got deeper into the material, the concentration remained relatively low, reaching 29.99 mg/l at 150 mm depth. Similar to the bacillus megaterium at pH 9 sample, bacillus stearothermophilus at pH 9 leads to lower chloride concentrations. At pH 9, the impact of bacillus megaterium on chloride resistance is less apparent. The bacterial-infused specimens generally show a reduction in chloride concentrations compared to the control, but the differences are not as significant as at pH 4. The 10-5 concentration appears to have a more substantial effect compared to lower concentrations (10-7 and 10-9). At the 15 mm depth, the concentration was 204.94 mg/l. The concentration decreased with depth, reaching 49.98 mg/l at 150 mm depth.

The introduction of both bacillus megaterium and bacillus stearothermophilus, at pH 4 and pH 9, significantly reduces chloride penetration and concentration at the surface and throughout the material's depth compared to the control sample. Lower chloride concentrations at all depths suggest improved durability and resistance to chloride-induced deterioration in the presence of these bacteria. Lower pH (pH 4) appears to enhance the effectiveness of the bacteria in reducing chloride penetration, evidenced by lower concentrations at similar depths compared to samples at pH 9. At pH 9, bacillus megaterium shows a more consistent reduction in chloride penetration compared to bacillus stearothermophilus.

Overall, bacterial-mortars specimens tend to exhibit improved resistance to chloride penetration compared to the control, with the effectiveness varying based on bacterial type, concentration, and pH level. The positive correlation between bacterial concentration and chloride resistance is more apparent at pH 4 than at pH 9, *Bacillus megaterium*, especially at higher concentrations, demonstrates a more consistent and pronounced reduction in chloride penetration compared to *Bacillus stearothermophilus*. This shows that bacterial interventions (*Bacillus megaterium*)

CONCLUSIONS

This research examined the performance of calcined clay in cement with bacteria-infused content under both acidic and alkaline conditions exhibits robust performance. It showed that bacteria mortar incorporated with calcined clay gave a good potential as replacement for cement. This is an indicator that bacterial precipitation and calcined clay incorporating of the mortar pore structure assisted in refining the interconnected pore spaces in the mortar specimens. These properties of bacterial concrete proved to

Figure 3: Chloride Penetration of Specimens at pH 4

Figure 4: Chloride Penetration of Specimens at pH 9

have the potential to enhance the durability of calcined clay cement mortar against chloride-induced deterioration.

The results support the hypothesis that these bacteria, when introduced to the calcined clay cement mortar, can enhance its resistance to chloride ingress, which is crucial for increasing the material's service life in chloride-rich environments. These results suggest that the introduction of specific bacteria and pH adjustments can be a promising approach to enhance the durability and chloride resistance of calcined clay cement mortar.

be promising in the realm of structural engineering. This research examined the performance of calcined clay in cement with bacteria-infused content under both acidic and alkaline conditions exhibits robust performance. For *Bacillus megaterium* mortars at pH 4, the chloride penetration and concentration are significantly reduced compared to the control sample. The presence of *Bacillus stearothermophilus* at pH 4 also results in a notable reduction in chloride concentration. When *Bacillus megaterium* was introduced at pH 9, the reduction in chloride concentration was even more significant. Similar to the *Bacillus megaterium* at pH 9 sample, *Bacillus*

steaerothermophilus at pH 9, samples had a lower chloride penetration when compared to pH 4. The introduction of both *bacillus megaterium* and *bacillus steaerothermophilus*, at pH 4 and pH 9, significantly reduced chloride penetration and concentration at the surface and throughout the material's depth compared to the control sample. Lower chloride concentrations at all depths suggest improved durability and resistance to chloride-induced deterioration in the presence of these bacteria. However, each of the bacteria performed better according to the pH. *Bacillus megaterium* does well in pH 4 while *bacillus steaerothermophilus* performed better in alkaline condition. Therefore, sodium chloride penetration tests revealed that bacterial interventions contributed to improving the material's resistance to chloride ingress. Higher concentrations of chloride were observed in control when compared to bacterial-infused specimens indicating enhanced durability and resistance to deterioration in chloride-rich environments. Hence, the bacterial mortar offers better resistance to chloride penetration and underscore the potentials of using bacterial treatments in enhancing the performance of construction materials.

It showed that bacteria mortar incorporated with calcined clay gave a good potential as replacement for cement. This is an indicator that bacterial precipitation and calcined clay incorporating of the mortar pore structure assisted in refining the interconnected pore spaces in the mortar specimens.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1: Chloride Penetration of Specimens at pH 4

Depth of slice (mm)	Chloride penetration			pH 4			
	Control	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁵	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁷	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁹	B. Str 10 ⁻⁵	B. Str 10 ⁻⁷	B. Str 10 ⁻⁹
15	404.87	279.91	399.88	384.88	264.92	219.93	189.94
35	354.89	149.95	299.91	179.94	159.95	199.94	124.96
50	324.9	129.96	149.95	99.97	104.97	149.95	124.96
65	269.92	89.97	129.96	69.98	39.99	109.97	124.96
80	259.92	89.97	54.98	59.98	29.99	49.98	124.96
95	239.93	89.97	39.99	54.98	29.99	49.98	119.96
110	229.93	79.98	39.99	54.98	29.99	39.99	104.97
125	224.93	79.98	39.99	39.99	19.99	39.99	104.97
150	199.94	79.98	39.99	39.99	14.99	39.99	104.97

Appendix 2: Chloride Penetration of Specimens at pH 9

Depth of slice (mm)	Chloride penetration			pH 9			
	Control	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁵	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁷	B. Meg 10 ⁻⁹	B. Str 10 ⁻⁵	B. Str 10 ⁻⁷	B. Str 10 ⁻⁹
15	404.87	179.94	294.91	249.92	204.94	279.91	294.91
35	354.89	99.97	174.95	179.94	139.96	149.95	174.95
50	324.9	89.97	109.97	99.97	64.98	119.96	108.87
65	269.92	29.99	79.98	79.98	64.98	99.97	78.98
80	259.92	29.99	69.98	49.98	59.98	89.97	65.82
95	239.93	29.99	69.98	49.99	59.98	54.98	65.82
110	229.93	29.99	69.98	49.99	54.98	29.99	65.82
125	224.93	29.99	64.98	49.99	54.98	29.99	65.82
150	199.94	28.00	64.98	19.99	49.98	28.00	65.82